

Research Article

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Effectiveness of Opay ORide outdoor advertisements on market expansion in Akure metropolis

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Abstract: The research looked at the effectiveness of Opay Oride's outdoor advertisements for market expansion in Akure metropolis, Capital of Ondo State, Nigeria. The framing theory was used as the theoretical framework. The survey research method was employed, and the questionnaire and interview guide were used as data collection tools. Three hundred and eighty-six (386) respondents were chosen using a multi-stage sample approach. Two Opay sales agents in Akure were interviewed. According to findings, most respondents were exposed to Opay outdoor advertisements in Akure, particularly the billboard in Akure's Ijomu neighbourhood. Respondents could largely remember Opay's price reduction (promo) and advertisements with the phrase "Where you matter." Findings further revealed that patronage increased dramatically after enormous Opay Oride outdoor advertisements in Akure and a significant degree of exposure to it.

It was concluded that Opay Oride outdoor advertising has considerable effectiveness in market expansion in the Akure metropolis. It is recommended, among other things, that the company continue to use outdoor advertising media to reach out to its target customers to outperform competitors.

Keywords – Advertisement, Akure residents, Market expansion, ORide patronage, Outdoor advertisements

1. INTRODUCTION

Trying to influence people's purchasing decisions and getting them to try out advertised products and services is a top priority for advertisers in the rapidly evolving 21st century. This is accomplished via the use of a variety of techniques to disseminate ideas and promote products to a specific audience. Advertising plays a critical part in promoting and total sales of that product because it has the power to shape customer attitudes, behaviour, preferences, and purchasing choices about a product (Belch & Belch 2009). The more visually appealing an advertisement is, the more likely it is to increase product sales than a less visually appealing one. According to Kotler, Wong, Saunders and Armstrong (2001: 16), "outdoor advertising achieves this objective by influencing the decisions, behaviour, preferences, and attitudes of potential consumers towards a product or service, through explicit visual expression of the goods, thereby fostering market expansion among the target audience."

Many forms of media, including newspapers, magazines, billboards, television, and the internet, now constantly inundate the public with vast advertising information (Latif & Abideen, 2011). The problem is that customers have so many things going on at once that they don't have time to keep up with the latest trends. And the advancement in technology is further polarising them in ways difficult to explain. This means that marketers will have a harder time catching them. Therefore, they are turning to outdoor advertising to reach their target audience even when

they aren't around. It is used to raise awareness of a product and increase sales. Billboards, it turns out, have a distinct set of traits (Kelley & Jugenheimer, 2004; Sissors & Baron, 2002; Taylor, 1997; Woodside, 1990). Through it, advertisers may target a certain geographic area to get buyers for their goods. Compared to other forms of advertising, outdoor advertising certainly has the longest-lasting influence of any marketing technique (Katke, 2007). As a result, outdoor advertising is becoming more and more popular as a subject of academic study.

In recent years, billboard advertising has played a more significant role in Nigerian product marketing. Product marketing through billboards increased despite the rise of electronic media. Advertising agencies that specialise in billboard advertising have sprung up due to this boom in billboard advertising and its electronic billboards version in Nigeria, which advertisers recognise as subsidiaries of the Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria (APCON, 2000). As a result of the billboard's locational flexibility, the audience is inundated with and exposed to advertisements daily. Good colour reproduction makes it a useful reminder for purchasers who buy on the spur of the moment. Recently, ride-sharing services like Uber and Lyft have grown more popular and serve millions of people every day. The Norwegian browser firm *Opera*, popularly known as *Opay*, established *Oride* in 2019 as an offshoot, with a strategy to diversify its business. Thus, it is observed that *Opay* has financed outdoor advertisements to expand *Oride's* market among Akure people; hence this research evaluates its efficacy.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

According to Nwoka, Ezirim and Maclayton (2005), many are asking whether outdoor advertising has a real impact on market growth and consumer buying behaviour in a major way or whether it has a negligible effect. According to Maclnis and Jaworski (1989), adopting Cohen, academics have been constructing ideas to explain, interpret, and forecast consumers' attitudes toward outdoor advertisements since the 1950s. As a result, billboard advertisements' effects on consumer choice have been hampered by the public's varying degrees of intellectual reasoning and visual perception skills. In some cases, opponents argue that the aesthetic design idea is objectionable. In contrast, in other cases, they argue that the physical construction is a waste of resources and a distraction to the public. This seems to be why many people believe that outdoor advertising, particularly billboards, has little effect on potential consumers' buying attitudes. There seems to be little empirical research in Nigeria to ascertain these conflicting views. Whereas, most of the available studies (Ojo, Oyeniran & Adekunle, 2020; Igwe & Nwaizugbo, 2020; Zeqiri, Ibraimi & Zufferi, 2019) on outdoor advertising are not carried out to look at its effectiveness for market expansion: whereas, very few of these studies are carried out in Nigeria. With this gap in the literature, it becomes pertinent to study the influence of outdoor advertisements for market expansion within the Nigerian context, focusing on *Opay Oride's* outdoor advertisements in Akure. This is apt for the study because *Opay* heavily financed outdoor advertisements to expand *Oride's* market among Akure people. *ORide* is a bike-hailing service that aims to tackle the transportation problem of overcoming the traffic and getting passengers to their destination faster.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following are the questions this research work tries to provide answers to:

1. To what extent are Akure residents exposed to *Opay Oride's* outdoor advertisements?
2. To what extent can Akure residents recall and recognise the *Opay Oride* slogan?
3. How far does *Opay Oride's* outdoor advertisement persuade Akure residents to use its services?
4. To what extent is the increase in the patronage of *Opay Oride* after six months of the outdoor advertisements?

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

Advertising is one of the best ways for businesses to compete in an increasingly competitive and rapidly changing global marketplace. As the market changes and competition increases, the ability of organisations that manufacture comparable items to utilise market communication components professionally and logically becomes more important to their success. To fulfil their company goals and obtain a competitive edge over their business

competitors, these considerations necessitate that companies engage in promotional efforts. The importance and necessity of advertising as a model of producer-to-consumer communication for today's businesses is obvious if we consider that distance between producer and consumer has widened steadily since the turn of this century; as a result, direct communication between these two groups has become unavailable.

Nearly everyone is now subjected to an increasing amount of advertising. In newspapers and magazines, on television and radio in the form of different entertainment programs, on billboards and signs in the streets and transit vehicles such as buses, trains, tramways, and ferry boats, advertising may be found almost everywhere at any time. As a constructive endeavour, advertising contributes to the economy by enhancing media facilities and permitting the greatest living standards for people, which aids cultural development, and has an invaluable educational structure.

Advertisement success depends on whether or not the right medium is used to convey or communicate it, regardless of how well planned and relevant it may be. An advertising medium is a means of reaching many potential customers with a marketing message. A well-thought-out media strategy aims to get the most impact for the least amount of money. There are two primary types of media in this genre: Print and digital media. Digital media, also known as broadcast media, focuses on radio and television. In contrast, print media includes newspapers, posters, magazines, journals, packaging, and other miscellaneous media like handbills, brochures, and catalogues. Poster, billboard, kiosk, gantry, and hoardings are examples of outdoor advertising mediums or Out of Home (OOH). New advertising channels include the internet and the web (Kotler & Armstrong, 2010).

According to Kelley and Jugenheimer (2008), outdoor advertising enables firms to reach a wide audience in specific areas. This sort of media may reach a wide audience in the right hands. Customers are exposed to commercials more often since the 30-day advertising cycle for placement is the norm. It is worth noting that outdoor advertising may be placed in various locations. With the consent of the authorities, outdoor advertisements may be shown wherever. Outdoor advertising allows for a lot of room for creativity and possibilities to stand out from the clutter and draw attention to prospective customers. Outdoor advertising is unquestionably successful, particularly when used with promotional tools, allowing businesses to contact customers even while away from their homes. However, outdoor advertising has the same limitations as any other media. Kelley and Jugenheimer (2008: 47) claim that messages may capture a product's essence in two seconds. Still, it is hard for marketers to display the brand in its best light for such a long period because of the fast turnover in public transportation. Meanwhile, consumers may quickly tire of repeated exposure to the same advertising if used at a high-frequency rate.

Nevertheless, research has established the efficiency of outdoor advertising. They have shown that billboard advertising plays an active part in marketing and impacts customers' purchasing behaviour by changing the current market dynamics. For example, Zuferi, Zeqiri and Ibraimi (2019) studied the effect of billboard advertising on customer purchasing behaviour. Secondary and primary data were employed in the research. A well-designed questionnaire was used to gather the bulk of the information. Two parts of a questionnaire were utilised to gather data using the survey approach. 306 North Macedonian citizens participated in the survey. SPSS statistical software is used to examine the obtained data. According to the findings, people value billboard advertising and believe it influences their purchasing choices. With these findings in mind, corporations may employ them in outdoor advertising. The study also established a substantial correlation between image, textural quality, and location of billboard advertising. The findings reveal that billboards are more successful if they include eye-catching graphics, numbers, and clear text.

The impacts of billboard/poster advertising on Awka consumers' use of home video rentals were explored by Igwe and Nwaizugbo (2020). A survey was utilised to obtain the main data. At the same time, a multiple-choice 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was employed to acquire the necessary data for the study. A sample size of 395 participants was selected from 33,400 students. Multivariate Linear Regressions (MLR) were used to test hypotheses in tables (MLR). Findings indicated that consumers who see billboards/posters advertising home videos are more likely to buy them. In addition, it was discovered that sizes and models had a beneficial influence on customer

preference for home video, but no significant association was established. To sum it up, billboards and posters are still an efficient form of advertising in the outdoors.

Students in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria, were influenced by digital billboard marketing while making smartphone purchase decisions (Ojo, Oyeniran & Adekunle, 2020). Students from the University of Ibadan and Lead City University were asked to participate in a survey to determine the impact of digital billboard advertising on their smartphone buying choices. Purposive sampling was used to choose 950 university students from the two participating institutions. In the findings, digital billboard advertising was shown to be a factor in the purchasing of smartphones by the vast majority of students. When it came to digital billboard exposure, Infinix was the most popular smartphone brand. The electronic/video-like billboards were the first digital billboards that had the power to influence consumer purchasing choices.

5. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

To define his approach to framing theory, Goffman (1974) coined the phrase "Frame Analysis." He said that people utilise their primary framework to understand what is going on in the world around them. According to Goffman (1974), there are two types of primary frames: natural and social. Both are used to help with data interpretation. The concept of framing theory is that the media attracts attention to particular incidents and then contextualises them. According to the notion, how something (such as advertising) is presented to the audience (known as "the frame") influences the judgments people make about how they understand that information. Framing is an abstraction that aids in the arrangement or shaping of the meaning of communication so that one is influenced. In this way, they may be seen as a kind of second-level agenda-setting in that they tell the audience what to think about advertising (according to agenda-setting theory) and how to think about them. They influence how the public perceives outdoor advertising (second-level agenda setting, framing theory). Outdoor advertisements often use slogans, language, contrast, and intrinsic symbolic objects. This improves their recall value and capacity to connect with the target audience.

As a consequence of the frames, prospective purchasers are more inclined to acquire the offered items. The framing theory is relevant to this study since every outdoor advertising is designed and created around a certain frame that is thought to entice buyers to buy. Although it is outside the scope of this research to investigate the frames used in *Opay Oride* outdoor advertisements, it is assumed that framing is present in all advertisements. The main issue here is its efficacy in increasing patronage.

6. RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a survey as a method of collecting data. The survey technique is often used to collect a large quantity of data from a broad range of people economically (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2003). People in Akure exposed to *Opay* outdoor advertising (estimated at 690,533 in 2021 by the World Population Review) were the intended audience. The sample size (386 participants) was determined through Wimmer and Dominick's online sample calculator. The multi-stage sampling approach selected three hundred and eighty-four (384) participants to gather the quantitative data. Multi-stage sampling is a method in which the operation is carried out in stages, using successively smaller sample units. Two distinct areas comprised the Akure metropolis: Akure South and North. In the first stage, Akure South was selected because of the heavy presence of *Opay* advertisements in that area. Afterwards, Akure South was split into 11 wards—specifically, *Aponmu, Gbogi/Isikan I, Gbogi/Isikan II, Ijomu/Obanla, Lisa, Oda, Odopetu, Oke Aro/Uro I, Oke Aro/Uro II, Oshodi/Isolo and Owode/Imuagun* — from which seven wards were chosen at random by balloting in a process known as simple random sampling. This was done in the second stage of the process. The seven previously chosen wards were further stratified into streets in the third, from which four random streets were purposefully selected. Respondents were chosen from the specified streets at the last stage of the process, depending on their availability and willingness to participate. The data were gathered using a standardised questionnaire. A face-to-face interview was done with two *Opay* agents in Akure for the

quantitative data. Descriptive statistics were used to examine the data. Simple frequency tables were used to address specific research questions.

7. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The data gathered from the field were presented and analysed. The preliminary data were first presented before the data that answered the research questions. The data were tabulated and interpreted appropriately.

7.1. Data presentation for quantitative data

Table 1: Showing the age bracket of the respondents

<i>Age Bracket</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
17 – 20	64	17
21 – 24	100	26
25 – 28	170	44
29 and above	50	13
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

The analysis presented in table 1 above showed that most of the respondents are between the ages of 25 – 28.

Table 2: Showing the gender of the respondents

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	164	42.7
Female	220	57.3
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 2 indicates that the majority of the respondents are females. These could be because they were most available during the administration of the instrument.

Table 3: Showing the Occupation of respondents

<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Students	257	67
Civil servant	50	13
Trader	34	9
Artisan	25	6
Unemployed	18	5
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 3 above reveals that out of 384 sampled respondents, 257 students represent 67% of the entire sample size.

Table 4: Showing whether respondents have seen any *Opay* outdoor advertisements in Akure

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	384	100
No	-	-
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 4 above reveals that all the 384 respondents that were sampled have seen *Opay* outdoor advertisements in Akure. This implies that *Opay's* advertisements are placed in strategic locations in Akure, where all eyes could see.

Table 5: Showing how often respondents see *Opay* outdoor advertisements in Akure

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Always</i>	320	83
<i>Very often</i>	50	13
<i>Sometimes</i>	14	4
<i>Rarely</i>	-	-
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 5 above reveals that out of 384 sampled respondents, 320 say they always see *Opay* outdoor advertisements in Akure. This analysis represents 83% of the entire sample. None of the respondents indicated that they rarely see *Opay* advertisement implies that *Opay* employs outdoor advertisements in Akure.

Table 6: Respondent often see *Opay* advertisements in Akure

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Oyemekun</i>	40	10
<i>Oke-Ijebu</i>	24	6
<i>Oke-Aro</i>	60	16
<i>Ijomu</i>	200	52
<i>Others</i>	60	16
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

To ascertain exact locations where respondents have seen *Opay* advertisements, Table 6 above revealed that out of 384 respondents, 200 (52%) say that Ijomu is the location where they often see *Opay* advertisements in Akure. In contrast, 184 (48%) say that they see *Opay* advertisements in different other locations in Akure. From the analysis, it was discovered that Ijomu is the location where they often see *Opay Oride* advertisements in Akure. This could be because of its popularity in Akure. But, it is factual that *Opay Oride* advertisements could also be seen in other locations.

Table 7: Showing the number of times respondents have seen *Opay* advertisements in Akure

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1-2	10	3
3-4	24	6
5-6	70	18

7 and above	280	73
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 7 above revealed that 280 say they have seen *Opay Oride* advertisements in Akure 7 times and above. This represents 73% of the sample size. As such, most of the respondents have seen *Opay Oride* advertisements in Akure 7 times and above. This indicates high exposure to *Opay* employing outdoor advertisement messages in Akure.

Table 8: Showing the *Opay* outdoor advertisements that respondents see the most

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Billboard	204	53
Lamp Post Banners	50	13
Transit Advertising	40	10.5
Bus stop Advertising	90	23.5
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 8 above revealed that out of 384 sampled respondents, 204 (53%) say that billboard is the *Opay Oride* outdoor advertisements that respondents see the most, followed by 90 (23.5%) who were exposed to Bus stop. This comes from the fact that most targeted and prospective *Opay Oride's* services customers are often at the bus stop or on the move. Hence, the company puts up its advertisement there to achieve high exposure.

Table 9: Showing what respondents can recall from *Opay's* advertisement

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Price Discount	44	12
Services	70	18
Promo	220	57
Others	50	13
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 9 above reveals that out of 384 respondents, 220 (57%) say they can recall promo price discounts from *Opay Oride's* advertisement. In contrast, 70 of them (18%) say that they say that recall services from *Opay's* outdoor advertisements. From the analysis, it is discovered that the majority of the respondents can recall promo and services from *Opay Oride's* advertisements. The implication of this is that *Opay* uses more promo and services as its advertisement strategy.

Table 10: Showing the slogan of *Opay* that respondents know

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Seamless mobile money services	60	16
Make dreams happen	80	21
This is where you matter	204	53
Can't remember <i>Opay's</i> Slogan	40	10
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 10 above reveals that out of 384 respondents, 204 (53%) says that the slogan of *Opay Oride* that respondents know is this is where you matter, while 80 (21%) say that they can't remember *Opay Oride's* slogan Make dreams happen. This finding implies that Opay employs a slogan that helps endear customers to the brand and gives a sense of belonging.

Table 11: Showing whether respondents have patronised Opay's services after exposure to outdoor advertisement

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	350	91
No	34	9
Total	384	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 11 above reveals that out of 384 sampled respondents, 350 (91%) say they have patronised *Opay Oride's* services after being exposed to their outdoor advertisements. In contrast, 34 (representing 9%) say that they have not patronised *Opay Oride's* services. This indicates that most respondents say *Opay Oride's* services have patronised them after being exposed to their outdoor advertisement. This implies that *Opay Oride's* outdoor advertisement is very effective.

Table 12: Showing how often respondents have patronised Opay services

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Always	200	57
Very Frequently	77	22
Occasionally	73	21
Never	-	-
Total	350	100

Source: Survey, 2021

Table 12 above reveals that out of 384 sampled respondents, 200 (57%) say that they have always patronised *Opay* services. In contrast, only 73 (21%) say that they occasionally patronise *Opay Oride* services. The majority of the respondents have been patronising the services of *Opay Oride*. The implication is that *Opay Oride's* outdoor advertisement has significantly achieved the objective for which the advertisements are done, which is to induce patronage and increase sales.

7.2. Data Presentation for qualitative data

The concerned research question seeks to find how *Opay Oride* outdoor advertisements have propelled residents to patronise its services in the Akure metropolis.

What was Opay's patronage in Akure like before major Advertisements?

In answering the above question, the *Opay Oride* sales agent, Mr David Duro Gbola, said:

Before major Advertisements, I could confirm *Opay Oride* wasn't a household name here. It wasn't familiar with more than 10% of the Akure population, with masses opting for the traditional known quick way of getting motorbikes on the roadsides for transportation. I'd conclude, it had very low patronage.

What was the major strategy deployed to increase patronage?

In answering the above question, Mr David Dúró Gbola said:

At *Opay Oride's* arrival, *Opay* had to compete with the local way of being transported to and fro to destinations. A major strategy deployed is vigorous advertisements and promotions on services rendered to commuters around Akure and its Environ. We even created a unique way of being transported by *Opay Oride* agents, just by ordering for them in the convenience of their homes and with ease without having to be on the roadside for long. This was innovative and a major boost to our patronage.

Another sales agent, Mr Alafisayo, said that: "Advertisement was the major key, we had our fliers all over the city, we had bills boards around the city that showcase our services and benefits which I believe captivate the interest of the Akure people and its environs to work with us." Apart from the strategies mentioned, Mr David Dúró Gbola said: "in cities like Lagos and Ibadan, we came up with the strategy of going from street to street telling them and explaining better why they need to patronise us and the benefit of working with us."

Has there been an increase in the level of patronage after the Advertisements in the Akure metropolis?

In answering the above question, Mr David Dúró Gbola said:

To a large extent, there was an increase; it created awareness about how easy it was to get transported from your doorstep to your destination and vice versa, which any Nigerian would want to opt-in for, for the sake of convenience, I'd say it did increase the patronage. From about 10 percent of patronage, we can discuss a 90 percent increase.

What were the changes seen after six months of Opays' outdoor adverts?

Mr David dúró Gbola responded: "There was a massive improvement in patronage, easy access to being transported, and job creation, at least to those the company needed to employ."

Mr Alafisayo added that:

Opay Oride got a lot of changes; we surveyed after 4 months. Then we discovered our brand has taken over 85.7% of the city. We have our apps in almost 95% of people using smartphones in the city, and our POS occupied like 80% of POS centres in the city". He concluded that it is an encouraging number. "The survey was carried out after 4 months of the outdoor advertisements, imagine how the increase will be in another 4 months.

8. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

According to table 5, most respondents (83 percent) saw *Opay* outdoor advertisements daily in Akure. Table 6 findings revealed that Ijomu is the most frequently encountered *Opay* outdoor advertisement in Akure. In contrast, tables 7 and 8 show that most respondents (73 percent and 53 percent, respectively) had seen *Opay* advertisements in Akure seven times or more, with billboard and bus stop advertisements topping the list of the most frequently seen *Opay* outdoor advertisements in Akure. These findings suggest a significant level of exposure to *Opay's* outdoor advertisements in Akure. The public is saturated with and exposed to advertisements regularly due to the billboard's locational flexibility, as illustrated in table 6. Because of the good colour reproduction, it is a great reminder for customers who buy on the spur of the moment. As a result, Belch and Belch's (2009) claimed that outdoor advertising might reach people that conventional media cannot. This is particularly true when marketers regard outdoor advertising as their main means of communicating with their target demographic. It also supports Jugenheimer's (2008) notion that outdoor advertising allows firms to reach many people in local markets. As seen by this research, this outdoor advertising media may have a significant amount of reach when used correctly. Given this, Zuferi, Zeqiri and Ibraimi (2019) reveal that billboards are more successful in reach if they include eye-catching graphics, numbers, and clear text. Also, Igwe and Nwaizugbo (2020) noted that outdoor advertisements have high exposure because of their strategic location.

Table 9 reveals that most respondents can remember a promotional price decrease from *Opay's* outdoor advertising; however, table 10 reveals that the slogan of *Opay* that respondents readily recall is "This is where you

matter," with 53% expressing so. Personal selling and sales promotion are the major components of a firm's promotional activity since they connect with clients and potential buyers.

According to table 11, most respondents (91 percent) were motivated to use *Opay*'s services after viewing their outdoor commercials. Similarly, table 12 data demonstrated that *Opay*'s outdoor advertising prompted most respondents (57%) always to utilise their services. This research backs up Rasim, Jusuf and Sadudin's (2019) claim that outdoor advertising has a major impact on capturing customers' attention. Zuferi, Zeqiri and Ibraimi (2019) established a substantial correlation between image, textural quality, and location of billboard advertising. The findings reveal that billboards are more successful if they include eye-catching graphics, numbers, and clear text. This finding confirms the argument of framing theory that the media attracts attention to particular incidents and then contextualises them. According to the notion, how something (such as advertising) is presented to the audience (known as "the frame") influences the judgments people make about how they understand that information. In this regard, the *Opay Oride* promo and slogan resonate well with Akure respondents.

According to the qualitative data findings, *Opay Oride* was only recognised by 10% of the Akure population before the outdoor advertisements, showing extremely low patronage. Outdoor advertisements have been regarded as the most significant critical approach employed to increase *Opay Oride* patronage in Akure. *Opay* distributed leaflets across the city and placed billboards in strategic spots to emphasise the unusual and intriguing services they provide. Advertising is one of the most effective forms of marketing for organisations striving to prosper in an environment of greater competition and rapid change due to globalisation. According to the data, there has been a considerable increase in the usage of *Opay* services after the formation of awareness, which has resulted in the creation of jobs. This is consistent with Zuferi, Zeqiri, and Ibraimi (2019) finding that people value billboard advertising and believe that it influences their purchasing choices. Also, Igwe and Nwaizugbo (2020) found that billboards and posters are still an efficient form of advertising in the outdoors. In support of this finding, Ojo, Oyeniran and Adekunle (2020) found that digital billboard advertising was a factor in the purchasing of smartphones by the vast majority of students.

9. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

This research demonstrates the extent to which survey participants in Akure, Ondo State, were exposed to *Opay Oride*'s outdoor advertisements, as well as the efficacy of the advertisements in terms of patronage. Furthermore, although other types of marketing require some effort, outdoor advertising is unusual in that we are subjected to direct and involuntary exposure to messages.

10. CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

With scant literature on the relationship between outdoor advertising exposure in Nigeria, this research adds to knowledge in the field of the debate of the significance or function of advertisement in the marketing process, from manufacturing to product introduction to the market and market growth. This study's results will, no doubt, serve as a reference for future research.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The promotional component of *Opay Oride*'s advertising should be featured more prominently in its outdoor campaign, as promotion is known to generate impulsive patronage among customers. Phrases that are extremely appealing to the target consumers should be used frequently to entice people to visit the business.
- ii. Because Akure residents would not have utilised *Opay Oride*'s services if they had not seen any of its outdoor advertisements, the brand should continue to employ outdoor advertising media to reach out to its target consumers to perform positively above rivals.

12. CONCLUSION

This study focused on *Opay ORide* outdoor advertisements in Akure metropolis to assess how effective they were at expanding the market. Findings conclude that *Opay ORide* outdoor advertising has a significant influence on Akure metropolitan consumers' patronage of *Opay ORide* services. It is also concluded that location and content are essential factors when considering outdoor advertising. Billboards continue to be a successful marketing tool for market expansion due to their broad reach and capacity to capture attention, leading to instantly sales.

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